

QUESTIONNAIRE FOR THE PAPER

Arina Kudriavtseva, Nisar Ahmad Hotak, and Olga Gadyatskaya. 2025. My Code Is Less Secure with Gen AI: Surveying Developers' Perceptions of the Impact of Code Generation Tools on Security. In The 40th ACM/SIGAPP Symposium on Applied Computing (SAC '25), March 31-April 4, 2025, Catania, Italy. ACM, New York, NY, USA, 10 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3672608.3707778>

Information Sheet

I have read the above information about the study

Yes

CONSENT

I agree to participate in this study

Yes

No

Q1 Which of the following best describes your current occupation?

Student

Hobbyist Programmer

Professional Programmer

Researcher

Freelancer Programmer

Other: _____

Q2 How many years of experience do you have in software development?

- Student/learning
 - 0 to 2 years of professional experience
 - 3 to 5 years of professional experience
 - 6 to 8 years of professional experience
 - 9 to 11 years of professional experience
 - More than 11 years of professional experience
-

Q3 What programming languages do you primarily use? (Select up to 3 from the list below)

TypeScript

Python

JavaScript

Ruby

Java

C++

C#

PHP

Go

other _____

Q4 How proficient are you at writing secure code **Without** AI tools in the language you use most?

- Beginner – I can write a correct implementation for a simple function
- Intermediate - I can design and implement secure programs, but I still have some concerns about potential vulnerabilities
- Advanced – I can design and implement complex, secure system architectures with a high degree of confidence in the code’s robustness

Q5 How proficient are you at writing secure code **With** AI tools in the language you use most?

- Beginner – I can write a correct implementation for a simple function
- Intermediate - I can design and implement secure programs, but I still have some concerns about potential vulnerabilities
- Advanced – I can design and implement complex, secure system architectures with a high degree of confidence in the code’s robustness

Q6 In your opinion, what are the perceived benefits of using generative AI in code security?
(Select all that apply)

- Increased Efficiency
- Automatic generation of patches for vulnerabilities
- Faster development
- Improved detection of vulnerabilities
- Improved code maintainability
- Others: _____

Q7 In your opinion, what are the perceived risks of using generative AI in code security?
(Select all that apply)

- Overreliance on AI without human oversight
- Introduction of new vulnerabilities
- Integration challenges with existing security tools
- Privacy and ethical concerns in AI-generated solution
- Likely to generate code with similar vulnerabilities
- Integration challenges with the code/infrastructure
- Others: _____

Q8 Five years from now, which of the following challenges related to security do you foresee for AI-generated code?
(Select all that apply)

- Integration challenges with the code / infrastructure
- Lack of transparency and auditability in AI-generated code
- Integration challenges with existing security tools
- Privacy and ethical concerns in AI-generated code
- Unintended biases in generating specific code
- I am not sure / I don't foresee any specific challenges
- Others: _____

Q9 The following statements represent **changes** in developers' **Behaviors**

	Strongly disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Strongly agree
I spend less time writing code with GAI compared to writing myself	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I am more cautious about deploying GAI code to production compared to deploying without GAI	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I spend more time on security reviews when using GAI code compared to code written by myself	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I find it less challenging to understand the logic behind GAI code compared to the code I write myself	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

I find it more important to document the purpose and limitations of GAI code for future reference compared to the code I write myself

Q10 In your opinion, what other changes in BEHAVIORS occur?

Q11 Which security best practices do you recommend developers follow when using generative AI code (GAI)

(Select all that apply)

- Choose GAI tools from reputable vendors with a focus on security
- Thoroughly review and understand all AI-generated code before integration
- Use active code scanning tools to identify vulnerabilities
- Do not enter sensitive or personal information into the generative AI tools
- Incorporating secure coding standards and guidelines
- Others: _____

Q12 Which security practices do you use when coding using generative AI tools?

Q13 When reviewing generative AI code, how important do you consider the following security factors :

(Please rank from 1 (most important) to 5 (least important))

- _____ Absence of known vulnerabilities in the generated code
- _____ Clarity and understandability of the code
- _____ Alignment of the generated code with secure coding best practices
- _____ Integration with security analysis tools
- _____ Reputation and Security track record of GAI tool

Q14 In your opinion, what other security factors are important when reviewing generative AI code?

Q15 Do you believe the security of code generated by different generative AI tools varies significantly?

- Yes
- No
- Not sure

Q15A Which of the following factors do you believe contribute most to the differences in security between generative AI tools?

(Select all that apply)

- Reputation of the tool
 - The specific functionalities of the tool (e.g., code completion vs. full program generation)
 - Transparency and explainability of the generated code
 - The availability of security features within the tool itself
 - Regular updates and patching of the tool
 - Others: _____
-

Q15B In your opinion, what other factors contribute to the differences in security between different generative AI tools?

Q16 Which generative AI tools do you use for coding?
(Select all that apply)

Github Copilot

Tabnine

OpenAI CodeX

IntelliCode

ChatGPT

Other 1: _____

Other 2: _____

Other 3: _____

Q17 How confident are you in the security of code generated by the selected Generative AI tools?

	Not Confident at All	Somewhat unsure	Neutral	Somewhat Confident	Very Confident
Github Copilot	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Tabnine	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
OpenAI CodeX	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
IntelliCode	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
ChatGPT	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other 1:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other 2:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Other 3:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Q18 Code completion vs. Full program generation:

"There is a higher risk of security vulnerabilities in code generated by full program creation tools compared to code completion tools."

- Strongly disagree
 - Somewhat disagree
 - Neither agree nor disagree
 - Somewhat agree
 - Strongly agree
-

Q19 How confident are you in the security of code generated by generative AI compared to code written by yourself?

- Not confident at all
 - Somewhat unsure
 - Neutral
 - Somewhat confident
 - Very confident
-

Q20 To receive the findings of this research, kindly share your email address with us.
